

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE THINKING ABILITY OF PRIMARY CLASS PUPILS BASED ON INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Abstract. *The article provides information on the development of creative thinking in students on the basis of interactive methods. The PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) International Assessment Program included basic concepts and "4K" principles about the direction of evaluating creative thinking*

Keywords: creativity, PIRLS, assessment, collaborationism, communicatively, critical, research, analysis, creative assignments.

INTRODUCTION

The world of modern information and communication technologies is developing very quickly. Internet, data transmission network has become a habit for a person who lives with modern requirements. Wherever a person lives, high technologies are becoming an integral part of him.

Communication technologies are one of the important factors influencing the development of society and the change of people's lifestyle. Their application makes it possible to use the achievements of world science more effectively, creates a real opportunity to conduct business effectively, informational interaction of people ensures their access to local and global information resources and their satisfaction of social and personal needs for information products and services.

The modern education system requires a serious restructuring, because in modern conditions it compares its informative and permanent character, in personal conditions and forms society, it is necessary to approach creatively with methodical, systematic, creative thinking. Turning a child into a creative, creative thinker depends on the technology of the pedagogical process. Effective organization of lessons in today's educational system, students being active and able to fully express their thoughts during the lesson depends not only on the teacher, but also on the students.

In the Decree of the President of Uzbekistan No. PD-60 dated on January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" and other regulatory legal documents related to this field, the educational system priority tasks aimed at improving and thereby forming the qualities of creative thinking of students have been determined.

Students being active and mobile during the lesson gives an effective result in the lesson. Creative thinking is more than generating ideas. Creative thinking is a concrete skill based on knowledge and experience that allows a person to achieve better results in sometimes difficult situations.

Societies and organizations around the world increasingly need innovative knowledge and creativity to solve problems, which, in turn, increases the importance of innovation and creative thinking. To be more specific, the work of teachers is a complex, conflicting and long-lasting process aimed at educating a well-rounded person.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Today, PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) is an international assessment system that assesses the quality of reading, comprehension, and expression levels of primary school students in different countries. started to be used. At this point, the question of how to prepare students for PIRLS, which determines the level of international assessment, is on many minds.

This requires great skill and competence from pedagogues. It is desirable to develop students' creative thinking in primary education. The process of teaching literacy in primary education consists of teaching elementary reading, writing and listening. Literacy is one of the most serious issues not only in pedagogy, but also in social life.

Special attention is paid to the literacy of every person in our independent country. In the process of teaching the student to read and write elementary reading and writing, there is a requirement for students to be active and engage in speech activities, the need to be able to express their thoughts orally, to express them in writing, and a situation that creates the need should be created.

Reading and writing skills ensure the successful implementation of one and the other. That is why teaching to read and writing is carried out at the same time and this activity is practiced regularly. Therefore, in the process of teaching literacy, a child should read and write a lot.

Increasing the creativity of students in the process of teaching literacy, in order to develop the qualities of creativity in students, it is necessary to first know the content of this concept. Creativity is derived from the English word "create" which means "to create". Creativity is an integral part of human thinking and spirituality that develops the student.

It is manifested not in the versatility of the student's knowledge, but in the pursuit of new ideas, making unexpected and unusual decisions in the process of solving life problems, that is, creativity cannot be achieved by repeating the given knowledge. the student's imagination also plays an important role in the process of creative thinking.

In order to show the creative abilities of students during literacy training, it is important for the teacher to tell the beginning of a story and leave the continuation to the discretion of the student, to finish a half-drawn picture, to express a creative opinion on the given picture, to recommend works of art that require creative thinking. have

Currently, the study of creativity of elementary school students is of particular importance, so many practical observations are being made. Interest in the use of interactive methods and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day.

One of the reasons for this is that until now, in traditional education, students were taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, and the use of modern technologies allows them to search for the knowledge they acquire, independent study and thinking, analysis. even teaches them to draw their own conclusions.

In this process, the teacher creates conditions for personal development, formation, learning and upbringing, and at the same time performs the functions of management and guidance. Today, in education "Brainstorming", "Thought storming", "Networks" method, "Sinquain", "KWL", "Fifth plus", "6x6x6", "Debate", "Role-playing game", Modern technologies such as FSMU, "Working in small groups", "Rounded snow", "Zigzag", "I will say the last word" are used. "Fifth (sixth, seventh ...) plus" method.

This method is particularly important for students to acquire logical thinking skills. When using it, the following actions are performed. Forms a system of concepts that serve to reveal the content of the subject being studied.

In order to encourage students to interpret the essence of their actions, to strengthen the topic, students are required to comment on the concepts preserved in the system and justify the logical connection between them. Analytical reasoning also requires the ability to express the most important underlying concepts.

RESULTS

When applying the method, the following actions are organized: the teacher creates a system of basic concepts that are not related to the subject in equal proportion; students determine the main concepts related to the topic and not related to the topic, and remove the main concepts that are not relevant from the system; students explain the result of their actions.

Using this method to strengthen a new topic in the study of topics such as "Kitchen equipment", "Birds", "Pets and poultry" in the 1st grade textbook gives a positive result. In this case, four words related to the topic and one irrelevant (extra) word (concept, idea) are given. Students identify this word (concept, idea).

For example: A tree grows green in one place.

Or, if proverbs such as Love is in two eyes are given, then the following picture can be presented to encourage students to think creatively and increase their interest.

The method of "Associations" can also be effectively used in lessons for elementary school students. The steps of performing the "Associations" method are carried out as follows.

Description: Each group of students is given a piece of paper with a word or sentence related to the study of the future topic. Under it, students write down the imagination that this word or sentence embodies in front of their eyes. For example: a visual paper is written in a vertical direction related to the chosen topic. Participants describe and write their imaginations for each letter of this word.

You can also use the "Find half of the egg" method to help students create new words. In this, the egg shape is divided into two parts and the continuation of the syllable written on the first part is written between the syllables on the other egg parts. For example: in the first piece of the egg, the second syllable written Ak - syllable is found and combined with the mal-syllable. The word Akmal is formed in the whole egg.

DISCUSSION

Through creative students, we can determine the extent to which schoolchildren acquire the skills to reflect changes in the education system, analyze events that are needed in real life, draw conclusions from them, and engage in communication, and how well the education system adapts to these changes.

The use of interactive and modern methods in primary classes is the basis of effective organization of the educational process. The use of modern information and communication

technologies will help students to think independently, expand their creative logical thinking, connect what they learned in lessons with life, and increase their interest in the lesson.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the development of students' creative thinking abilities in classes will further develop the competence of each student. A creative student can think freely and be active in various situations, as well as in the process of completing tasks given in international assessment studies.

We can say that the use of interactive and modern methods, information and communication tools in primary school classes causes students to think modernly and creatively and serves to increase the quality and efficiency of the lesson. For this, each of us needs to work selflessly, looking at our subject responsibly.

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